

Review On Leveraging Web-Based Technology for Smart Student Accommodation Management Using AI Driven Solutions

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Abstract-- For the students pursuing higher education, finding appropriate housing is a headache because typical accommodation search methods sometimes overlook the affordability, allocation, healthy environment and personal preferences. By offering personalized, useful features and improving user experience, artificial intelligence (AI) can completely transform student housing finding system, as per this study. Artificial intelligence (AI) can help to find appropriate accommodation options as per the need like location, safety, and budget by utilizing algorithms. Mainly this type of website can help to find the students of same batch or steam can be located close to each other that's how they can study properly and get better environment , then the schedule management system that can help the night time scholars and the dawn scholars to allocate in different room. AI problem solving can reduce stress involved with traditional techniques. Some times students gets into a fraud while signing any contract, by using AI featured contract

management guarantees the transparency of agreements, so that it reduce risks. Also it closes the gap of communication between the landlord and the students. The study gives an idea how AI can help students by highlighting the difficulties such as insufficient support networks and providing useful features. This also gives the wider path of AI driven problem solving. The study concludes by outlining suggestions for the proper application of these technologies and discussing ethical issues including bias in AI systems and data privacy. This study discuss on evolving AI to solve real world challenges.

Keywords-- Artificial Intelligence, Student accommodation management, web application, Algorithms, Block chain, NLP.

I. INTRODUCTION

Finding appropriate housing has become a major challenge for students pursuing higher education in the quickly changing educational landscape of today. In order to access high quality educational institutions, both domestic

and foreign students move to urban and suburban areas, which has drawn a lot of attention to the issue. Finding suitable housing is difficult due to a number of interconnected factors, such as shifting rental markets where prices of all properties fluctuate at the same time, geographic restrictions, increased competition for housing close to universities where housing costs are higher, and students' highly individualized preferences. Affordability, comfort, safety (particularly for girls), and accessibility including being close to their educational institutions, having dependable transportation, having poor food, having expensive daily necessities, and having access to local amenities are frequently included in these preferences.

While students come for study from different places they usually don't know about the area near study center . So that they rely on college hostels or find room in traditional way like such word of mouth from someone or manually searching. It becoming less effective and takes so much time. This type of short time decision making can make several problems like stressful situations and inappropriate housing management might result difference scenarios those will pull back students to study properly. This things head up to unclear rental agreements, deposit agreement, food related issues. This caused the problem to find better solution of housing. There are many solution

available but the data is not managed properly for the students.

As the challenges could found , there is a need for different unique approaches that can organize the data set of housing management system. For solving this problem artificial intelligence is a game changer tool. AI can transform the way students approach to find housing because of its real time data processing, analysis and large cloud database. AI filters can identify the choice of the students as per their spending limits, preferred location and other small but important preferences by utilizing random forest algorithm, NLP and predictive analytics. Furthermore information on like commute time, neighborhood atmosphere and the price swing, AI based platforms can improve a lot more efficient ways to handle these things to make easy decision. AI models can not only help to improve student and landlords contact but also enter in leasing process. Most importantly for overseas students who are not familiar with the language or culture or cannot understand local housing markets so that sometimes they got scammed. Using AI based model the transparency will be there in the process. AI driven innovations not only benefits educational sector also can help to grow a strong pillar for government, private or corporate sectors to merge with the educational sector properly.

This study aims to find out the difficulties students encounter in finding suitable accommodation, assess how AI technologies can help with these difficulties, and look at the possible long-term effects of AI-powered solutions on the ecosystem surrounding student housing and discusses about some techniques like NLP, random forest algorithm. By doing this, it hopes to draw attention to how crucial it is to incorporate cutting-edge technologies into conventional institutions in order to develop a more student-centered approach to accommodations.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study based on our qualitative and descriptive approaches. We are focusing on our literature review of 13 papers and research articles that we found from online. This review paper searches for the best result can be get using AI with block-chaining , random forest algorithm and NLP together. To get guarantee result the step by step approach is important. In this paper we are discussing about all 13 papers literature review and some data published on online articles to get a better understanding about this system. This paper employs a systematic methodology. Scholarly databases such as IEEE Xplore, Springer, Elsevier, ACM Digital Library and online articles were thoroughly searched. To find pertinent studies,

keywords such as student housing management, hostel management systems, AI in student housing, IoT for housing, and block chain in hostels were used . With the exception of foundational publications (Louise 2009), studies released in the previous five years were given priority, the basic simple structure is being searched to get a user friendly system with better functionality. Some of the paper discussed about blockchain and AI both to build a secure and fast data processing, then again random forest algorithm introduced, NLP also the one thing highlighted in (Mali et al. 2024). The process we are following to complete the review paper is :

A. Literature review table- We reviewed 13 papers mainly within 5 years published, in a systematic papers some of them are conference papers, also journals, books are there in the table. Every paper describes unique technologies that can be used in the system to fix the student problems. There in the table we talk about dataset used, techniques to find out the solutions, the results after applying the techniques, limitations and the future scope. This data help to study the problems in a fast and unique manner and there will be a chance to combine all these solutions and give a identical solution.

B. Findings and discussions- The study finds the use of new models or technologies like random forest algorithm use(Mali et al. 2024),

double diamond design process(Mohd Nizam et al. 2021), qualitative and quantitative analysis(Usman, Bello, and Raji 2024), web based technology(Ganorkar et al. 2021), Decision Support System (DSS), Rule-Based Algorithms(Rasoanaivo and Zaraté 2024) etc.

C. Challenges & Limitation- In the study many challenges and limitations we found. Some of them are like implementation cost high,

technical skill gap, infrastructure limitations, privacy and security, scalability, maintenance, efficiency etc.

D. Conclusion- Despite of these limitations there could be some improvement could be done like study more about these problems, improve AI interactions, hybrid housing management system, expand to global standard etc.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW TABLE

Table 1 A literature review table of 13 research papers and thesis:

No	Title	Year	Dataset	Models/Techniques	Results	Limitations	Future Scope
1	<i>A Usability Review of Undergraduate Student Web Portals at University of Ibadan (Osunade, Adetimirin, and Asoro 2024)</i>	2024	University of Ibadan student portals	Modified University Portal Usability Assessment Index	Identified usability gaps and proposed an improved web portal for students	Limited to a single university	Expansion to other universities, more usability testing
2	<i>An Indoor Navigation Support for the Student Halls of Residence Using Augmented Reality: A Design Perspective(Mohd Nizam et al. 2021)</i>	2021	71 students (survey) + 4 evaluators (prototype test)	Marker-Based AR, Unity 3D, Vuforia SDK, C# scripting	AR improves the way of look the room without present there physically	Implementation cost is high and it is hard to integrate with student accommodation management	Connecting with AR opens so much digital opportunity to satisfy consumers
3	<i>Yan Whale—An Integrated Life Service Platform Design for College Students(Liu and Zhao 2024)</i>	2024	Peking University Smart Campus Data	Integrated Service Platform	Designed a one-stop digital service for campus life, including accommodation	No standardization across universities	Expansion to different universities, AI integration
4	<i>Study of Hostel Room Allocation Using Random Forest Algorithm</i>	2024	MIT Academy of Engineering, India	Random Forest Algorithm	Improved hostel room allocation efficiency	Limited real-world implementation	Expansion to larger datasets, additional ML models for

	<i>(Mali et al. 2024)</i>						allocation
5	<i>Challenges of Student Housing in Islamabad(Usman, Bello, and Raji 2024)</i>	2024	Islamabad Hostels	Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis	Issues with student housing, such as congestion and a lack of amenities	Restricted to a single area	Studying hostels in different cities and nations in comparison
6	<i>Web-Based Application for Quick Finding of Housing and Food in a City(Ganorkar et al. 2021)</i>	2021	Nagpur, India	Web-Based System	Developed an online platform for hostel and food accommodation search	No AI-based recommendation system	Incorporation of AI for personalized search and predictive analytics
7	<i>An Intelligent Student Hostel Allocation System Based on Web Applications(Azeta et al. 2021)</i>	2021	Web-Based Student Hostel Data	Automatic Allocation System using PHP & MySQL	Improved hostel allocation through automation	Lacks real-time student preference integration	AI-driven personalized allocation
8	<i>Hostel Management System (HMS)(Narkhede et al. 2022)</i>	2022	Mumbai Hostel System	Web-based Hostel Management System	Simplified hostel booking, rent tracking, complaint handling	No predictive maintenance integration	Use of IoT for maintenance tracking
9	<i>Designing and Implementing Accommodation Management System: ASHAMS as Case Analysis(Riaz and Bhowmik 2022)</i>	2022	NSTU, Bangladesh	Web-based Accommodation Management System	Designed ASHAMS for efficient hostel management	Pilot project, limited dataset	Large-scale implementation, smart card integration
10	<i>Student Residence Management System(Louise 2009)(thesis)</i>	2009	University of Western Cape	Online Booking & Allocation System	Improved residence application process	Outdated technology	Migration to cloud-based architecture with modern security protocols
11	<i>Digital Transformation in Student Living: A Design Case Study on Overcoming Dormitory Challenges(Bhandari 2024)(thesis)</i>	2024	Case study on dormitory challenges	Digital transformation framework, UX design principles	Improved student living experience through smart technology	Limited to specific dormitory case study; lacks large-scale validation	Expansion to various student accommodations; AI-driven automation
12	<i>SAGeLogE: A Decision Support</i>	2024	Accommodation management	Decision Support System (DSS), Rule-	Optimized student	Requires real-time data integration	Integration of AI for better

	<i>System for Students' Accommodation Management(Rasoa naivo and Zaraté 2024)</i>		datasets	Based Algorithms	accommodation allocation	for dynamic updates	recommendation accuracy
13	<i>The Role of Accommodation Environments in Student Mental Health and Wellbeing (Worsley, Harrison, and Corcoran 2021)</i>	2021	Surveys and psychological assessments	Statistical analysis, Mental Health Index	Found strong correlation between accommodation quality and student well-being	Lack of experimental control; mostly observational	Development of intervention strategies for improving accommodations

IV. FINDINGS & DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of 13 chosen publications reveals a number of significant developments in the administration of student housing. In Figure 1 bar chart shows adoption rates of different technologies to build a smart system. **Figure 1** shows the adoption rate of different models after implementing. The approaches can be used in student housing management systems are:

Figure 1: Adoption rate of technologies

1. Enhancing Resident Experience with Natural Language Processing (NLP)- Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a type of

artificial intelligence that helps computers understand and respond to human language in a way that feels natural as like human chatting. In student housing, this technology can make communication with students would be futuristic, easier and faster. NLP can help to do real time communication between students and housing owner. Chatbot can learn everytime anyone ask any question, so time by time the message can solve every question by giving needed answers. Basically it will reduce administrator burdon.

2. Machine Learning (ML)- ML increases the efficiency and equity of hostel assignments by automating room allocation and suggestions. For example ML is subset of AI, and it keeps learning from the data allows AI to work on improved data. ML identifies patterns & make predictions rather than pre-programmed data.

3. Internet of Things (IoT)- Makes it possible to monitor hostel amenities in real time,

improving maintenance plans and resource usage. In IoT smart sensors can be used like sensors, cameras, real time availability and facility condition updates, room occupancy updates regularly, and other basic things need to manage accommodation can be done by IoT features.

4. Block chain Technology- It uses decentralized transaction records to improve security and transparency in the management of accommodations. Block chain ensures secure and transparent transactions of data(Worsley, Harrison, and Corcoran 2021). For example it can be used to keep immutable record of listing and do agreement of contract without third party.

5. Web-Based Systems- It allows for the centralized administration of student housing by providing online reservations, complaint resolution, and facility monitoring(Azeta et al. 2021; Ganorkar et al. 2021; Rasoanaivo and Zaraté 2024). It needed some of the skills like react, node.js, HTML, CSS, JS, Mongo DB, SQL, PHP to be developed.

6. Random forest algorithm- Random forest algorithm predicts user needs as per observing behaviour of the student while using the website or application(Mali et al. 2024). It's a machine learning techniques and follows supervised learning to observe historical data and preferences. It could help to set budget and other preferences.

7. Double diamond design process- This is a maintenance process ,by having regular surveys, usage of the system, user research noticed and give a proper result of problem statements that can be solved.

8. Qualitative and quantitative analysis: These techniques can help to maintain the system by regular surveys or noticing regular customer engagements (Usman, Bello, and Raji 2024).

9. Decision Support System (DSS): It helps to follow a systematic way to solve the preferences based on rule based algorithm.

V. CHALLENGES & LIMITATIONS

Even with major technological developments, a number of issues still exist:

Scalability Problems- A large number of suggested systems (Louise 2009; Ganorkar et al. 2021) are not scalable and are made for

Figure 2 : Cost vs Efficiency for technologies

particular universities.

High Implementation Costs- Widespread adoption of IoT and blockchain-based solutions

is challenging due to their high initial investment requirements. **Figure 2** shows the graph of cost to implement the model and as per the cost the how efficient the system will be.

Privacy and Security Issues- Web-based hostel systems are susceptible to online attacks.

ML Models with Data Bias- Machine learning studies brought to light problems with biased datasets that result in unjust room distributions.

Efficiency issues - There should be lag or latency in the web server because of the hybrid use of features.

Global standards- Its hard to standardize the level of the system the global system needs. It need to have massive database, connections, security, govt approval, and lastly main thing is to manage accommodation data without any redundancy or corruption.

VI. CONCLUSION

By using many of these technologies together the accommodation finding system can be more flawless. Web based platform can be the foundation layer provides the interface to connect all the features like booking, payments, searching can be done on this page. then AI and ML comes in the picture , to make the website smart web platform by observe, learn and predict from the available data it improves the user interaction. Also AI can involve in agreement management so that no third party

can involve in it and it could be transparent and secure. Then NLP can help to humanize the experience like someone searches for "rooms near greater noida under the range of 6000" it can be understand by the computer using NLP. Blockchain can help to secure the database and maintain transparency. It can make sign digital agreements.

Merging all the technologies together is one of the challenge that can be solve in future. This hybrid model will personalize the experience, latency free communication, secure , transparent and also it works on real time data so its scalable.

Recent developments in student housing management systems have been thoroughly reviewed in this study, with an emphasis on cutting-edge technology like blockchain, the internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), and web-based platforms. Automating room allocation procedures, cutting down on manual labor, and improving resource distribution have all been made possible by AI and machine learning models. IoT based solutions help by providing real-time monitoring of lodging amenities, which enhances both student comfort and operational effectiveness. Blockchain technology improves the financial and transnational processes associated with student housing by increasing data security, transparency, and trust.

Notwithstanding these technological advantages, the research also pointed out important drawbacks that prevent these systems from being widely used. Data security flaws, bias in AI-driven allocation models, high implementation costs, and limited scalability across many institutional contexts are still problems. The shift from pilot initiatives to institution-wide implementations is frequently hampered by these issues.

Future studies must thus concentrate on creating hybrid models that integrate blockchain technology and artificial intelligence to enable safe, data-driven decision-making. Scalable, cloud-based solutions that can facilitate roll-outs across several institutions while guaranteeing data interoperability and system integration are also desperately needed. Furthermore, developing trustworthy and fair student housing management systems will need tackling algorithmic bias and bolstering cybersecurity measures.

To sum up, by addressing these issues, scholars and professionals may create the foundation for the upcoming generation of intelligent, safe, and incredibly effective student housing systems that can be tailored to regional and international learning settings.

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